

EUROCHILDREN RESEARCH BRIEF SERIES, NO.5

UK-BORN CHILDREN OF EU NATIONALS IN THE UK: HISTORICAL, NATIONAL AND LOCAL PERSPECTIVES

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

- This brief presents information about children of EU nationals in the UK via the use of birth registration statistics from England and Wales, Northern Ireland, and Scotland.
- Children of EU nationals born in the UK have not featured extensively in debates surrounding the EU Referendum. Yet, their demographic significance has been growing over time. Not only have they gained importance, but the countries of origin of the parents have also changed, as have the rates of births to mixed parentage.
- In 2016, the share of births to at least one EU parent amounted to about 12% of all births in England and Wales, 13% in Northern Ireland, and 10% in Scotland. These shares have been increasing, especially since the mid-2000s.
- These increasing shares can be linked to the inclusion of, and increase in, births to nationals from 'newer' EU Member States, especially those from the 2004 Accession.
- This also comes against the reduction of the share of births to Irish nationals over time, especially in Scotland and England and Wales. This picture is slightly different in Northern Ireland.
- We also see this change in the main countries of birth of parents, where the share of births to mothers and fathers from 2004 Accession countries has increased.
- Many of these births come from instances where both parents were born in the same EU country. Yet, 'mixed' births, where parents are born in different countries, have also tended to increase over time. This is not only for births with one parent born in the UK and one born in a EU27 country, but also, to a certain extent, for births where both parents are born in an EU country. This is especially relevant for parents born in EU14 countries.
- With regard to their geographical distribution in the latest period, births to EU-born parents were mostly concentrated in the East, in and around London, and along the Northern Irish border with the Republic of Ireland. The latter picture, however, changes slightly if we discount Irish-born parents from the picture.
- The distribution of births to EU-born parents in the various London Boroughs shows larger percentages of births in the north-western boroughs of the city. Births to parents born in EU8 countries being more at the periphery than births to parents born in EU14 countries.
- This oft-ignored segment of the population, of which exact estimates are difficult to come by, is thus growing. It is also changing in its composition and its geographical location varies widely. The potential implications of exiting the EU for these children are as yet unknown, but could have important ramifications.

DISCLAIMERS

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This briefing uses data from various sources. Below you can find more information about the specific sources and associated copyright statements.

All calculations presented here are the responsibility of the authors and comply with data disclosure guidelines.

England and Wales data

Office for National Statistics. (2017). *Births Registrations in England and Wales, 1982-2016: Secure Access*. [data collection]. 3rd Edition. UK Data Service. SN: 8043, <http://doi.org/10.5255/UKDA-SN-8043-3>.

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Scotland data

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Maps

Office for National Statistics; National Records of Scotland; Northern Ireland Statistics and Research Agency (2011). 2011 Census: boundary data (United Kingdom) [data collection].

UK Data Service. SN:5819 UKBORDERS: Digitised Boundary Data, 1840- and Postcode Directories, 1980-. <http://discover.ukdataservice.ac.uk/catalogue/?sn=5819&type=Data%20catalogue>

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INTRODUCTION

Debates around Brexit and EU migrants have tended to centre around the first generation of non-UK EU nationals living in the UK, and focus by far and large on the predicaments of the adult population. Yet, as we have seen in previous Eurochildren briefs¹, there are particular concerns that EU families have with regard to Brexit and the legal frameworks around the withdrawal from the EU will potentially affect the children of EU nationals born in the UK.

Very little is known about the UK-born children of EU nationals in the UK, who represented just over 12% of all live births in the year of the EU Referendum (according to our calculations). In this brief, we trace back their importance and the location of their birth around the time of the EU Referendum using birth registration data.

Data

The data used in this brief comes from birth registration data from three sources:

- (1) England and Wales: birth registration data from 1982 to 2016 from the Office for National Statistics²;
- (2) Northern Ireland: birth registration data from 1997-2016 from the Northern Ireland Statistics and Research Agency^{3,4}; and
- (3) Scotland: birth registration data from 1974 to 2016⁵ from the National Records of Scotland⁶.

In all three data sources, we were provided with specific information for all births in a given year allowing us to identify and locate births to EU nationals: date of birth (for Scotland, England, and Wales), country of birth of mother, country of birth of father, as well as geographical identifiers for parents residing in the UK. All figures presented in this brief exclude stillbirths and use 2016 geographies (which led to a small loss of data, along with births registered in a nation with parents residing in another). Certain figures are suppressed because of small counts and disclosure issues.

While this data gives us an upper estimate of the number of UK-born children of EU nationals, as the data source used here does not allow us to see whether people have moved since birth, it also provides a lower estimate of the number of children from EU nationals born outside of the UK. Recent estimates report the number of children of non-Irish EU nationals in the UK at around 900,000⁷.

² Office for National Statistics. (2017). [Births Registrations in England and Wales, 1982-2016: Secure Access](#). [data collection]. 3rd Edition. UK Data Service. SN: 8043

³ Note that the data provided only included yearly data, which means that estimates for years of change in EU memberships will include underestimations of EU births.

⁴ Northern Ireland Statistics and Research Agency – NISRA (2018). *Birth registration data (2997-2016)*. [data collection] Northern Ireland Statistics and Research Agency

⁵ Note that the data provided included 2017, but is not used here.

⁶ National Records of Scotland – NRS (2018). *NRS birth registration data (1974-2017)*. [data collection]. National Records of Scotland.

⁷ See Sumption, M and Kune, Z (2018) [Unsettled Status? Which EU Citizens are at Risk of Failing to](#)

¹ See Eurochildren Briefs no. 1, 2, 4, and 6.

Counting EU nationals

The data presented here classifies EU nationals based on EU membership at time of the birth (year of birth for Northern Ireland). This implies, as discussed in our earlier brief on EU nationals in the UK⁸, that births included different countries depending on the period of EU membership. The EU membership periods are as follows⁹:

- 1st January 1974 to 31st December 1980 (Scotland only): Belgium, France, Germany, Italy, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, Denmark, and Ireland;
- 1st January 1981 to 31st December 1985 (England & Wales from 1982): as above + Greece;
- 1st January 1986 to 31st December 1994: as above + Portugal and Spain;
- 1st January 1995 to 30th April 2004 (Northern Ireland from 1997): as above + Austria, Finland, and Sweden - this is considered the cut-off for the EU14;
- 1st May 2004 to 31st December 2006: as above + Czech Republic, Estonia, Cyprus, Latvia, Lithuania, Hungary, Malta, Poland, Slovakia and Slovenia – all countries except for Cyprus and Malta¹⁰ are counted as EU8;
- 1st January 2007-30th June 2013: as above + Romania and Bulgaria – these are considered as EU2;
- 1st July 2013 to 31st December 2016: as above + Croatia – this country and Cyprus and Malta are considered as EU Other.

Note that we also include births from countries/territories where EU (or UK) citizenship is conferred, such as some French overseas departments and Gibraltar¹¹, as this would make them exempt from immigration control.

[Secure their Rights after Brexit?](#), Oxford: Migration Observatory

⁸ Lessard-Phillips, L, Sigona, N. (2018) [Mapping EU citizens in the UK: A changing profile? From 1980s to the EU referendum](#), Eurochildren Research Brief Series, no.3, Birmingham: IRIS

⁹ See https://ec.europa.eu/neighbourhood-enlargement/policy/from-6-to-28-members_en

¹⁰ Both countries are part of the Commonwealth.

¹¹ European Commission (2016) Territorial status of EU countries and certain territories. Available at:

https://ec.europa.eu/taxation_customs/business/vat/eu-vat-rules-topic/territorial-status-eu-countries-certain-territories_en

OVERVIEW – UK-BORN CHILDREN IN THE UK

We first provide an overview of the number of births to EU nationals ('EU births') over time by data source, mainly because of the different time frames provided in the data. Figures 1 to 3 show the number of EU births by year (including years where new EU membership occurred): the number of EU births is represented on the left vertical axis, and the percentage of 'EU births' out of all registered births is represented on the right vertical axis. Here we differentiate between births where both mother and father were born in the EU (EU/EU); where one parent was born in the EU and the other in the UK (EU/UK); where one parent was born in the EU and the other outside of the UK and the EU (EU/NEUNUK); and where there was only 1 EU parent registered (EU only). Note that, in some instances, increases in numbers for EU births will be due to an increase linked to expansion of EU membership.

We first look at EU births for England and Wales (Figure 1). Up until 2004, EU births represented about 4% of all live births in a given year, with most births being from EU/UK parentage. From that point on, the percentage of births to EU parents steadily increased to just over 12% of all live births in 2016. From 2009 onwards, births from parents both born in the EU became more numerous, overtaking EU/UK parentage, which has remained more or less stable. Table 1 indicates that this may be linked to the increase in the number of births to EU8 parents. We also see a steady, but relatively low, increase in the number of births to parents from within and outside the EU, as well as a relatively stable number of births to EU/UK parents.

Table 1 Percentage of births to EU14/EU8/EU2&Others parents

		EU14	EU8	EU2&O
England & Wales	2004-2006	4.1%	1.2%	0.3%
	2007-2013	4.1%	4.0%	0.8%
	2013-2016	4.4%	5.6%	1.8%
Northern Ireland	2005-2006	8.5%	1.2%	0.1%
	2007-2013	8.0%	4.6%	0.4%
	2014-2016	7.1%	5.3%	0.7%
Scotland	2004-2006	3.2%	0.6%	0.1%
	2007-2013	3.3%	3.7%	0.3%
	2013-2016	3.7%	5.4%	0.7%

Source: ONS (2017), NISRA (2018), NRS (2018). Note that percentages may not correspond to other figures because of mixed parentage. See page 4 for disclaimers and copyright statements.

We now turn to the figures for Northern Ireland (Figure 2). In 1997, close to 7% of all births were from registrations with at least one EU parent, whereas it amounted to about 13% of all births from 2008 onwards (as we will see below, Irish nationals were largely responsible for earlier figures). Until 2007, the number of births of mixed parentage including a UK national accounted for more than half of EU births. Table 1 shows that, from 2004 onwards, this is mostly due to an increase in the births to EU8 nationals. The percentage of mixed EU births comprising a parent from outside the UK or the EU increased over time, but remained relatively low (under 2% of all birth registrations).

Turning to the figures for Scotland (Figure 3), we see similar patterns of relatively stable percentage of EU births until 2004 (around 3%), increasing to close to over 10% of births in 2016.

In a similar fashion to Northern Ireland, EU births with one parent born in the UK comprised the majority of births until approximately 2006. However, contrary to the picture in Northern Ireland, EU births to two EU parents overtook these from 2009 onwards. In the post-2004 period, births from parents with at least 1 EU8 parent account for a large percentage of births to 2 EU parents.

Figure 1 EU births in England and Wales, 1982-2016.

Source: ONS (2017). See page 4 for disclaimers and copyright statements.

Figure 2 EU births in Northern Ireland, 1997-2016.

Source: NISRA (2018). See page 4 for disclaimers and copyright statements.

Note that numbers in the years where there is an overlap in EU membership are underestimations (see Data section).

Figure 3 EU births in Scotland, 1974-2016.

Source: NRS (2018). See page 4 for disclaimers and copyright statements.

If we look at these figures by period of EU membership (looking at the percentage of various forms of parentage out of all births, given that periods, and hence numbers, will be different), we see the clear change in percentage over time. This is especially with regard to the increase in the percentage of births to 2 EU parents in the post-2007 period.

As we have seen from Table 1, this can also be linked to the increase in the number of births to EU8 nationals in all nations. Some of these percentages are, however, attributable to the presence of Irish nationals in the data, especially in Northern Ireland. We now turn to this issue.

Figure 4 Percentage EU births by EU membership period.

Source: ONS (2017), NISRA (2018), NRS (2018). See page 4 for disclaimers and copyright statements.

Irish nationals: changing importance over time

As discussed above and previously¹², and seen in many debates surrounding the situation of EU nationals in the UK, citizens born in the Republic of Ireland represent an interesting case to examine further. This is especially relevant for Northern Ireland, given its geographical location, as we will see in a subsequent section. Figures 5 to 7 show the number of EU births including (blue column) and excluding (red column) parents born in the Republic of Ireland over time for all three data sources. Again, increases and changes in the number of births can be linked to changes in EU membership. As we are only able to measure country of birth in the data, and not nationality, there is a chance that we are also capturing UK citizens within these figures. Figures from the 2011 Census showed that 24% of individuals born in the Republic of Ireland held a UK passport¹³.

In England and Wales (Figure 5), births with at least one parent from the Republic of Ireland comprised over 50% of EU births in the earlier period, steadily decreasing over time to just under 6% of EU births in 2016. Sharpest decreases in the percentage of births to Irish parents can be seen around the 2004 Accession period. Since 2009, the percentage of births to Irish parents has remained more or less stable.

¹² Lessard-Phillips, L, Sigona, N. (2018) [Mapping EU citizens in the UK: A changing profile? From 1980s to the EU referendum](#), Eurochildren Research Brief Series, no.3, Birmingham: IRIS.

¹³ Office for National Statistics (2013) Detailed country of birth and nationality analysis from the 2011 Census of England and Wales - Office for National Statistics. Available at: <https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/populationandmigration/populationestimates/articles/detailedcountryofbirthandnationalityanalysisfromthe2011censusofenglandandwales/2013-05-13>

Turning to Northern Ireland (Figure 6), we see that EU births with at least 1 parent born in the Republic of Ireland comprised a large share of the number of births. This is especially in the run-up to the 2004 expansion, where births with at least 1 Irish-born parent comprised around 84% of all EU births. Since then, especially 2008, this share has decreased to reach 42% of EU births in 2016.

The picture in Scotland (Figure 7) is quite different. In 2016, births to Irish-born parents represented only 10% of all EU births, compared to 64% at the start of the period covered by the data. From 2006 onwards, over 80% of EU births were to EU parents born outside of Ireland. Since 2012, that figure has been stable at around 10% of all EU births, with births with at least 1 parent from the Republic of Ireland accounting for 9.5% of EU births in 2016.

The picture shown in the figures below shows that the importance of births to Irish nationals has been quite different in Northern Ireland, England and Wales, and Scotland. In Northern Ireland, they represented, and still represent, quite a large share of what can be counted as an EU birth. As we will see later, this also has geographical implications.

Figure 5 EU births with and without Irish nationals, England and Wales.

Source: ONS (2017). See page 4 for disclaimers and copyright statements.

Figure 6 EU births with and without Irish nationals, Northern Ireland.

Source: NISRA (2018). See page 4 for disclaimers and copyright statements.

Note that numbers in the years where there is an overlap in EU membership are underestimations (see Data section).

Figure 7 EU births with and without Irish nationals, Scotland.

Source: NRS (2018). See page 4 for disclaimers and copyright statements.

Disaggregating parental origins

We have, so far, looked at aggregate groupings of births to EU nationals, which have given us a good overview of the situation. In this section, we investigate further by examining the main countries of birth of EU parents. Tables 2-4 show the main EU countries of birth of mothers and fathers, excluding the UK, for births with at least 1 parent born in the EU over the various periods for the three data sources.

Up until the 2004 Accession period, the main country of birth of parents in England and Wales was, unsurprisingly, Ireland. This was followed by Germany, and then France for mothers) and Italy (for fathers). Over this period, the share of births to Irish parents decreased from about a third of EU births to under a fifth. The share of births to German parents, however, increased slightly over that period.

Table 2 Main countries of birth of EU parents for EU births, England & Wales

Period	Main countries (% of EU births)	
	Mother	Father
1982-1985	Ireland (31.5%) Germany (14.3%) France (4.3%)	Ireland (32.1%) Germany (9.9%) Italy (8.4%)
1986-1994	Ireland (26.3%) Germany (17.2%) France (4.3%)	Ireland (27.4%) Germany (12.7%) Italy (6.1%)
1995-2004	Ireland (18.2%) Germany (18.0%) France (7.3%)	Ireland (17.3%) Germany (14.2%) Italy (4.5%)
2004-2006	Germany (13.0%) Poland (11.8%) Ireland (9.7%)	Germany (10.9%) Ireland (8.7%) Poland (8.3%)
2007-2013	Poland (29.0%) Germany (8.2%) Lithuania (5.1%)	Poland (22.3%) Germany (7.1%) Ireland (4.8%)
2013-2016	Poland (27.9%) Romania (10.3%) Lithuania (6.0%)	Poland (22.1%) Romania (9.6%) Germany (5.0%)

Source: ONS (2017). See page 4 for disclaimers and copyright statements.

From 2004 onwards, we see that the main countries of birth of parents switches. In the latter two periods, the share of births to parents born in Poland increased to over 28% for mothers and 22% for fathers. The share of births to Lithuanian mothers also increased, as well as those of Romanian mothers and fathers. Germany, however, remained in the main countries of birth for mothers until 2013 and for fathers until 2016. But the share significantly decreased.

Table 3 Main countries of birth of EU parents for EU births, Northern Ireland

Period	Main countries (% of EU births)	
	Mother	Father
1997-2004	Ireland (53.2%) Germany (6.4%) France (1.1%)	Ireland (44.9%) Germany (4.6%) France (0.8%)
2005-2006	Ireland (46.0%) Poland (5.3%) Germany (4.7%)	Ireland (41.4%) Poland (4.9%) Lithuania (3.8%)
2007-2013	Ireland (29.9%) Poland (20.5%) Lithuania (7.7%)	Ireland (30.3%) Poland (19.1%) Lithuania (6.8%)
2014-2016	Ireland (22.6%) Poland (20.9%) Lithuania (9.3%)	Ireland (25.7%) Poland (18.9%) Lithuania (8.1%)

Source: NISRA (2018). See page 4 for disclaimers and copyright statements.

A slightly different picture emerges from the Northern Ireland data (Table 3), where Ireland remained the main country of birth of both fathers and mothers. Their share, however, decreases over time. Over the period, the share of births to Polish mothers and fathers also increased, but remained at around 18-20% of EU births in the latter two periods. The share of births to Lithuanian mothers and fathers is also slightly higher than in England and Wales for those periods.

In Scotland (Table 4), the picture is somewhat similar to both England and Wales and Northern Ireland: Ireland and Germany have remained the top countries of births of mothers and fathers, but with a decreasing

share over time. In earlier periods, France, Italy, and the Netherlands were also among the top countries of births of parents. The share of births to Polish mothers and fathers has also increased, but is much higher in Scotland (close to 40% for mothers and around a third for fathers).

Table 4 Main countries of birth of EU parents for EU births, Scotland

Period	Main countries (% of EU births)	
	Mother	Father
1974-1980	Ireland (34.6%) Germany (10.4%) Italy (4.0%)	Ireland (33.1%) Italy (10.4%) Germany (7.8%)
1981-1985	Ireland (23.4%) Germany (17.8%) France (3.8%)	Ireland (24.2%) Germany (11.2%) Italy (10.1%)
1986-1994	Germany (23.8%) Ireland (18.5%) The Netherlands (3.6%)	Ireland (17.6%) Germany (16.3%) Italy (6.6%)
1995-2004	Germany (25.1%) Ireland (15.8%) France (5.5%)	Germany (17.3%) Ireland (13.0%) France (4.4%)
2004-2006	Germany (18.0%) Ireland (12.2%) Poland (9.1%)	Germany (13.9%) Ireland (11.5%) Poland (7.4%)
2007-2013	Poland (38.2%) Germany (9.4%) Ireland (6.9%)	Poland (33.3%) Germany (7.5%) Ireland (6.2%)
2013-2016	Poland (39.4%) Germany (6.5%) Ireland (5.5%)	Poland (32.6%) Germany (5.3%) Ireland (5.1%)

Source: NRS (2018). See page 4 for disclaimers and copyright statements.

Part of the mismatch between figures for parental country of birth can be linked to births with 'mixed' parentage, e.g. different parental countries of birth. As shown previously, the number of births to parents from within and outside the EU has increased over time. But we also need to consider instances where both parents are born in the EU. In Figures 8 to 10, we break down these

measures further. In Tables 5 to 7, we also explore the percentage of births to EU parents where country of birth is different for mothers and fathers.

Figure 8 and Table 10 show the prevalence of 'mixed' births for the England and Wales data. As we can see, there has been a general increase in the percentage of 'mixed' births including a parent from the EU and one from outside the EU (including the UK). The exception to this trend is for the share of EU14/UK births, which is somewhat decreasing. It is worth to note, however, that these percentages are quite low. Instances of 'mixed' births with EU parents from different origins increased but also decreased in latter periods. If we investigate 'mixed' births for differentiated EU groups (EU14/8/2&other), we see that rates of 'mixed' births are much higher for births to 2 parents from EU14 countries. Rates are, on the other hand, relatively low but increasing for births to parents from EU8 countries.

Figure 8 Percentage of 'mixed' births by EU period, England and Wales.

Source: ONS (2017). See page 4 for disclaimers and copyright statements.

Table 5 Percentage of 2 EU-parent births with parents born in different countries, England and Wales

	1982-1985	1986-1994	1995-2004	2004-2006	2007-2013	2013-2016
Parents born in different EU countries	5.97	7.9%	14.77%	13.99	9.3%	9.9%
Parents born in different EU14 countries				18.7%	20.8%	17.7%
Parents born in different EU8 countries				3.2%	3.8%	5.3%
Parents born in different U2/EUO countries				0.0%	0.3%	0.4%

Source: ONS (2017)

See page 4 for disclaimers and copyright statements.

Turning to Northern Ireland (Figure 9 & Table 6), we see that the rate of 'mixed' births is higher than in England and Wales, as is expected, but that the overall increase for EU/UK births and decrease in EU14/UK parental pairings follow a similar trend. This is, again, accompanied by an increase in 'mixed' births with a EU8 parent. With regard to mixed EU parentage, the share of births with parents from two different EU countries is relatively low, but increasing, in comparison.

Finally, with regard to Scotland (Figure 10 and Table 7), we see that the magnitude of 'mixed' births was similar to that of England and Wales in the latter period, but was lower in earlier periods. Again, the share of 'mixed' births increased, but remained relatively stable for births with EU14/UK parentage.

Figure 9 Percentage of 'mixed' births by EU period, Northern Ireland.

Source: NISRA (2018). See page 4 for disclaimers and copyright statements.

Table 6 Percentage of births with 2EU parents born in different countries, Northern Ireland

	1997-2004	2005-2006	2007-2013	2014-2016
Parents born in different EU countries	4.6%	3.9%	5.5%	8.4%
Parents born in different EU14 countries		3.7%	5.2%	6.3%
Parents born in different EU8 countries		ND	3.5%	5.9%
Parents born in different U2/EUO countries		0.0%	ND	0.0%

Source: NISRA (2018)

See page 4 for disclaimers and copyright statements.

Table 7 Percentage of births with 2EU parents born in different countries, Scotland

	1974-1980	1981-1985	1986-1994	1995-2004	2004-2006	2007-2013	2013-2016
Parents born in different EU countries	3.6%	7.3%	9.5%	14.6%	13.7%	7.3%	8.6%
Parents born in different EU14 countries					18.0%	21.0%	14.6%
Parents born in different EU8 countries					3.8%	3.3%	4.6%
Parents born in different U2/EUO countries					0.0%	ND	ND

Source: NRS (2018)

See page 4 for disclaimers and copyright statements.

Figure 10 Percentage of 'mixed' births by EU period, Scotland.
Source: NRS(2017). See page 4 for disclaimers and copyright statements.

BUT... WHERE WERE THEY?

The sections above have shown us that the share of births to EU parents has gained in importance over the various EU membership periods. In addition to having gained in importance, the countries of origin of the parents have also changed, as have the rates of births to mixed parentage. In order to continue with our investigation, we also want to explore the geographical locations of such births, in order to have a better idea of the potential presence of UK-born children of EU nationals in the UK, bearing in mind the aforementioned caveats. In this section, we look into the geographical spread of EU births for the latest period of EU membership, the one leading to the EU Referendum. On the maps that follow, we present EU births as a percentage of all births in a given district, which cover Local Authority Districts, London Boroughs, Metropolitan Districts, Unitary Authorities, Council Areas and District Council

Areas¹⁴. Local Authority Districts that are in shades of blue indicate those with lower percentages of EU births (the darker the lower), whereas areas in shades of red indicate higher percentages (the darker the higher). This colour scheme applies to all maps presented here.

¹⁴ Office for National Statistics (2018) Local Authority Districts, Counties and Unitary Authorities, (December 2017) Map in United Kingdom. Available at: <https://data.gov.uk/dataset/6ff3fc08-26ff-453e-9289-6420269ba10e/local-authority-districts-counties-and-unitary-authorities-december-2017-map-in-united-kingdom>

Figure 11 Percentage of EU births by Local Authority District, July 2013-December 2016.

Sources: ONS (2017); NISRA (2018), NRS (2018), Office for National Statistics; National Records of Scotland; Northern Ireland Statistics and Research Agency (2011). See page 4 for disclaimers and copyright statements.

As we can see from the map above, the geographical spread of EU births varies across the country, but is also concentrated in specific areas. The percentage of EU births is highest in Boston; the London Boroughs of Kensington and Chelsea, Haringey, and Harrow; Corby; Peterborough; and South Holland. In Northern Ireland, the Districts closest to Ireland have higher percentages of EU births. If we take Irish births out of the equation (see Figures 12), we see that EU nationals are spread out slightly differently, with higher percentages of EU births in Antrim, Armagh, Newry and Mourne, Cookstown and Belfast. In Scotland, the Council Areas of Edinburgh and Aberdeen City are those with highest percentages of EU

boroughs contain large shares of EU nationals (Lessard-Phillips and Sigona, 2018) within their overall population but not their foreign-born population leads us to dig a bit deeper into this situation.

Figures 13 to 16 show the percentage of EU births in the different London Boroughs. Here again, darker shades of red indicate higher percentages of births to EU parents out of all registered births in the Borough, whereas darker shades of blue indicate lower percentages. The overall picture (Figure 13) shows that the distribution is skewed toward the Northwestern parts of London. If we contrast it with the percentages of births to EU14 (Figure 16) and EU8 (Figure 15) parents,

Figure 12 EU births in Northern Ireland, including (left) and excluding (right) Irish parents.

Source: NISRA (2018), Office for National Statistics; National Records of Scotland; Northern Ireland Statistics and Research Agency (2011). See page 4 for disclaimer and copyright statements.

births. Figure 12 EU births in Northern Ireland, including Irish parents. Going back to the national picture, however, shows that there are some areas where EU births tend to be more prominent: this is especially the case in the East and East Midlands, and in and around London. The prominence of EU births in and around the capital, and the fact that we have shown in our previous brief that London

we see that births to EU14 parents are more concentrated within Central London, whereas births to EU8 parents are highest in the periphery.

Figure 13 Percentage of EU births in London Boroughs.
Source: ONS (2017), Office for National Statistics; National Records of Scotland; Northern Ireland Statistics and Research Agency (2011). See page 4 for disclaimers and copyright statements.

Figure 15 Percentage of EU8 births in London Boroughs.
Source: ONS (2017), Office for National Statistics; National Records of Scotland; Northern Ireland Statistics and Research Agency (2011). See page 4 for disclaimers and copyright statements.

Figure 13 Percentage of mixed EU births in London Boroughs.
Source: ONS (2017), Office for National Statistics; National Records of Scotland; Northern Ireland Statistics and Research Agency (2011). See page 4 for disclaimers and copyright statements.

Figure 14 Percentage of EU14 births in London Boroughs.
Source: ONS (2017), Office for National Statistics; National Records of Scotland; Northern Ireland Statistics and Research Agency (2011). See page 4 for disclaimers and copyright statements.

These forays into the geographical locations of EU births allows us to see the concentrated, yet also fragmented nature of the places where EU parents have settled prior to giving birth.

CONCLUSION

This work presented in this brief gives us an indication as to the importance of UK-born children of EU nationals in the different nations of the UK. Different configurations of parentage, including the changes in parental origins and in mixed parentage, show a changing landscape. The analysis presented here also indicates where the children of EU nationals are possibly growing up, and where we can expect to find a larger concentration of an oft-ignored segment of the UK population. This population has been increasing in importance over time but has also varied at different rates in the different nations of the United Kingdom. But it is nonetheless a fact that it is a growing segment of the population. Not only has it been increasing but, as we examine in other Eurochildren briefs, their legal status is at risk of being jeopardised by the legal reverberations of exiting the European Union. But, given the degree of parental mixing and spread in the UK, the ramifications of Brexit are likely to be felt by an even larger section of the British population and be passed to the next generation if not addressed promptly.